

Effect of Music Intervention on Basal Cardiovascular Parameters and Stress Levels in Hospitalized COVID-19 Patients**Mohit Mishra¹, Rachna Parashar², Shah Nawaz Alam³, Waqas Alauddin⁴, Saurabh Saigal⁵, Rajay Bharshankar⁶, Avinash Thakare⁷, Shashwat Arora⁸**¹Assistant Professor, Department of Physiology, Naraina Medical College and Research Centre, Kanpur, Uttar Pradesh, IND²Associate Professor, Department of Physiology, All India Institute of Medical Sciences, Bhopal, IND³Associate Professor, Department of Physiology, Naraina Medical College, Kanpur, IND⁴Assistant Professor, Department of Physiology, Naraina Medical College and Research Centre, Kanpur, IND⁵Professor, Department of Anesthesiology, All India Institute of Medical Sciences, Bhopal, Bhopal, IND⁶Professor, Department of Physiology, All India Institute of Medical Sciences, Bhopal, IND⁷Associate Professor, Department of Physiology, All India Institute of Medical Sciences, Bhopal, IND⁸Second year MBBS student, Naraina Medical College & Research Centre, Kanpur, IND

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Abstract:**Background:** COVID-19 patients in hospitals are susceptible to varying degrees of stress conditions: anxiety, fear, and depression. Music intervention is a cutting-edge method of treating patients in hospitals. This study aims at the effects of music intervention on basal cardiovascular parameters and stress levels in hospitalized COVID-19 patients, as well as the viability of introducing music intervention on-site with these patients.**Objective:** The study's objective is to evaluate the impact of music intervention in hospitalized Covid-19 patients' basal cardiovascular parameters and stress levels.**Methods:** Sixty hospitalized COVID-19 patients participated in the interventional study, which was conducted at AIIMS in Bhopal, India. They were equally divided into 2 groups: 30 patients in the intervention group and 30 patients for control. Basal cardiovascular parameters such as HR, SBP, and DBP, and stress parameters like serum cortisol and IL-1 levels were measured both before and after music intervention. Data was assembled and entered using Microsoft Excel, and it was analyzed using licensed statistical software, SPSS version 21.0 (IBM Corp., Armonk, NY).**Results:** In the post-music intervention group, HR (90.14 ± 14.35 vs. 84.43 ± 11.29 , $p < 0.000$), BP systolic (139.78 ± 17.67 vs. 133.46 ± 16.78 , $p < 0.000$), and BP diastolic (93.14 ± 13.77 vs. 88.56 ± 12.36 , $p < 0.000$), showed a significant decrease as compared to the pre-music intervention group. Serum cortisol (23.7 ± 6.45 vs. 19.65 ± 6.19 mcg/dl, $p < 0.000$) and IL-1 (139.12 ± 95.26 vs. 72.89 ± 66.43 , $p < 0.000$) also showed a significant decrease in the post-music intervention group. Whereas in the control group, HR (88.20 ± 13.94 vs. 88.07 ± 10.64 , $p = 0.877$), BP systolic (137.53 ± 22.59 vs. 136.33 ± 19.69 , $p = 0.349$), BP diastolic (90.80 ± 14.74 vs. 89.67 ± 13.34 , $p = 0.196$), serum cortisol (22.14 ± 7.13 to 21.96 ± 6.12 mcg/dl, $p = 0.934$), and IL-1 (142.17 ± 124.92 to 141.76 ± 122.79 , $p = 0.468$) all demonstrated a decline in the control group over the pre parameters, but was not significant.**Conclusion:** The study reveals that music intervention for hospitalized Covid-19 patients significantly improves basal cardiovascular parameters and stress levels. The findings demonstrate that it is feasible to provide music intervention to Covid-19 patients on-site as an inextricably linked non-pharmacological intervention.**Keywords:** covid-19 anxiety, fear and anxiety, serum cortisol, cardiovascular prevention, stress, music intervention, covid-19.This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.**Introduction**

The COVID-19 pandemic has resulted in serious health system problems, psychological suffering, and public anxiety. [1] During an uncertain time, hospitalized patients are separated from their families, which can cause stress disorders, depression, anxiety, and fear of dying, insomnia, agitation, dis-

comfort, pain, immobility, frustration, and an inability to unwind. [2,3] During a hospital stay, music intervention can be utilized as an adjunctive, non-pharmacological method to lessen stress and anxiety. [4] While music medicine (MM) involves passively listening to pre-recorded music supplied by

medical staff, music intervention involves the systematic application of musical experiences aimed at achieving therapeutic goals by a trained music therapist. [5] It has been demonstrated that music intervention is beneficial in treating both physical symptoms and psychological distress in patients with serious illnesses. [6] Inducing a state of relaxation without the need for medication, music intervention lowers blood pressure and respiratory rate, enhances sleep quality, lessens anxiety disorders during mechanical ventilation, and may have a beneficial effect on the use of tranquilizers and analgesics by patients on a ventilator. [7] However, there is a dearth of research on music intervention impact in hospitalized COVID-19 patients in India. The aim of this study is to assess the impact of music intervention in hospitalized COVID-19 patients. Specifically, the study will look at how music intervention may affect basal cardiovascular parameters and lessen discomfort and stress levels.

Material and Methods

This pre- and post-interventional research was conducted with ethical clearance. With approval from the institutional ethics committee with ethical number IHECPGRMD028, the research was taken place in the COVID ward in the All India Institute of Medical Sciences (AIIMS) in Bhopal, India, during June 2021 to December 2022. Written consent from the patients was obtained. This study included sixty hospitalized COVID-19 patients from both genders. Two groups of thirty patients each were assigned to the intervention group and the control group. Baseline cardiovascular variables were measured in both groups before and after music sessions. These included heart rate (HR), systolic and diastolic blood pressure (SBP and DBP), and stress indicators like IL-1 and serum cortisol levels. The study participants were those with years ranging from 40 to 65 who were taken to the COVID unit. This study did not include any patients with psychiatric or mental conditions, hearing impairments, or chronic pain syndrome.

The participants in the study wore headphones that played thirty minutes a day, spaced eight hours apart, of pre-recorded, low-pitched, low-volume instrumental music meant for relaxation and meditation. [5] This was done for a total of 72 hours. In addition, the control group got a pair of headphones, and the same amount of time was spent without any music. Music intervention was administered once, at 8 a.m., for a span of 30 minutes, 8 hours apart, for 3 days. After an overnight fast,

serum cortisol and IL-1 levels were measured in blood samples. The patients' blood levels of IL-1 were measured using the enzyme-linked immunosorbent test (ELISA). The test quantifies the binding strength of matched antibody pairs to the target. [8]

Statistical analysis:

Entry of data and assembly were performed using Microsoft Excel. Data analysis was done using a licensed analytical program, SPSS version 21.0 (IBM Corp., Armonk, NY). The standard deviation (SD) and mean were used to display the data. A non-parametric test called the paired Student t-test was employed to ascertain the statistically significant nature of the variations among the pre- and post-intervention assessments. If a p-value was under or equal to 0.05, it was regarded as significant.

Results

The 30 patients in the intervention group had a mean age of 52.50 ± 9.51 years, a BMI of 23.34 ± 1.34 , and 21 males and 9 females. In contrast, the control group consisted of 11 females and 19 males, with a mean age of 54.83 ± 11.80 years and a BMI of 22.78 ± 2.13 .

We examined pre- and post-data in both the interventional and control groups, measuring basal cardiovascular parameters such as heart rate (HR), systolic blood pressure (SBP), and diastolic blood pressure (DBP), along with stress parameters like serum cortisol and IL-1.

Basal cardiovascular parameters in the interventional group and control group

A comparison between pre- and post-music medicine parameters was conducted in the intervention group. Table 1 illustrates a significant decrease in all parameters in the post-music intervention group compared to the baseline pre-music intervention group: HR (90.14 ± 14.35 vs. 84.43 ± 11.29 , $p < 0.000^*$), BP systolic (139.78 ± 17.67 vs. 133.46 ± 16.78 , $p < 0.000^*$), and BP diastolic (93.14 ± 13.77 vs. 88.56 ± 12.36 , $p < 0.000^*$). In contrast, the control group's HR (88.20 ± 13.94 vs. 88.07 ± 10.64 , $p = 0.877$), BP systolic (137.53 ± 22.59 vs. 136.33 ± 19.69 , $p = 0.349$), and BP diastolic (90.80 ± 14.74 vs. 89.67 ± 13.34 , $p = 0.196$) all demonstrated a decline in the control group over the pre-parameters, but was not significant.

Table 1: Comparison of pre and post basal cardiovascular parameters in the music intervention group and control group

	Music Intervention group			Control group		
	Before (Mean ± SD)	After (Mean ± SD)	p-value	Before (Mean ± SD)	After (Mean ± SD)	p-value
HR (bpm)	90.14±14.35	84.43±11.29	0.000*	88.20±13.94	88.07±10.64	0.877
SBP (mmHg)	139.78±17.67	133.46±16.78	0.000*	137.53±22.59	136.33±19.69	0.349
DBP (mmHg)	93.14±13.77	88.56±12.36	0.000*	90.80±14.74	89.67±13.34	0.196

*p-value less than 0.05 is significant, SD- standard deviation, bpm- beats per minute, HR - heart rate, SBP - systolic blood pressure, DBP- diastolic blood pressure.

Stress parameters in the interventional group and control group

Serum cortisol and IL-1 levels were compared before and after intervention. Following the music intervention, there was a substantial decrease in serum cortisol levels, with a decrease from 23.79±6.45 to 19.65±6.19 mcg/dl ($p < 0.000^*$). Compared to the baseline, IL-1 declined in the post-music intervention group from 139.12±95.26

to 72.89±66.43; table 2 shows that this difference was statistically significant ($p < 0.000^*$). In contrast, serum cortisol in the control group decreased in the post-parameters from 22.14±7.13 to 21.96±6.12 mcg/dl ($p = 0.934$).

Compared to the baseline, IL-1 dropped in the post-parameters from 142.17±124.92 to 141.76±122.79, although the difference was not statistically significant ($p = 0.468$).

Table 2: Comparison of baseline and post-therapy serum cortisol and inflammatory marker in the intervention group

Stress parameters	Music Intervention group			Control group		
	Before (Mean ± SD)	After (Mean ± SD)	p-value	Before (Mean ± SD)	After (Mean ± SD)	p-value
Serum Cortisol (mcg/dl)	23.79±6.45	19.65±6.19	0.000*	22.14±7.13	22.56 ±6.12	0.934
IL-1	139.12 ±95.26	72.89 ± 66.43	0.000*	142.17±124.92	141.76±122.79	0.468

*p-value < 0.05 Significant, SD- standard deviation, IL- Interleukin

Discussion

The interventional group's physiological measures differ considerably from the control groups, indicating the effectiveness of music intervention. Following the music intervention, the intervention group revealed a significant decrease in heart rate and systolic and diastolic blood pressure, serum cortisol and IL-1 parameters.

Anxiety and stress can cause adverse responses to the sympathetic nervous system, leading to constriction, myocardial stimulation, and bronchoconstriction. [9] Music intervention can positively affect the parasympathetic system, resulting in a relaxation response and physiological changes such as muscle relaxation and deep breathing. [9] This is crucial for COVID-19 patients, who often experience increased breathing difficulty and fatigue. Previous studies have shown improvements in anxiety, pain, quality of life, heart rate, respiratory rate, blood pressure, fatigue, and emotional state. Music intervention is cost-effective, has no apparent risks, and can provide physical, emotional, and cultural benefits. However, there is a paucity of studies that have been conducted with COVID-19 patients in a complex and difficult setting. The emotional perception of music and its physical effects involve

catecholamines, but the therapeutic potential of music intervention should also involve attitudes, expectations, affects, imagination, memory, and bodily self-awareness. [10] The receptive music intervention technique used in this study helped patients find and connect to internal resources of confidence, cope with stress, and facilitate psychodynamic responses. [11] Using a music medicine intervention would involve patients passively listening to pre-recorded music without guidance and accompanied by a music therapist. Music intervention allows for realtime adaptation and modification of play lists based on verbal and non-verbal responses. [12]

Our results yielded similar findings of Golino et al., who looked at how an active music intervention affected patients in critical care units. [13] Similar to our study, according to Bradt and Dileo et al.'s findings, patients receiving mechanical ventilation who consistently listen to music see a reduction in their systolic blood pressure and respiratory rate, leading to a relaxing reaction. [7] They found reduced heart rate and hormone levels. [7]

A study reveals that music, as a non-pharmacological intervention, significantly impacts the physiological, psychological, and social responses of hospitalized COVID-19 patients. [14]

It decreases heart rate, blood pressure, breathing, pain intensity, anxiety levels, sleep disturbances, delirium occurrence, and improves cognitive function, which may be related to psychophysiological changes causing a decrease in the sympathetic nervous system. [14] We also found that serum cortisol levels and IL-1 were decreased after music intervention; the former had been significantly decreased, which had detrimental psychological impacts over time. It has been found that there is a relationship between the degree of surgical trauma and cortisol concentration and that cortisol is a major stress response signal. [15] In patients, the Chlan et al. study looked at cortisol, or inflammatory blood levels, as a possible sign of stress-related anxiety. [16] The study's findings were somewhat inconsistent due to patient comorbidities, acute renal failure or insufficiency, or drugs that may alter cortisol levels.

The study did not demonstrate a correlation between cortisol levels and music treatments as a means of lowering overall stress. [16] The effectiveness of the intervention is influenced by the choice of music, and music intervention is highly effective in reducing anxiety, pain, and agitation in confused patients. [14] Our findings also reveal the same.

Another study by Hunter et al. found that active music intervention has been shown to be an effective way to alleviate anxiety during the weaning off of mechanical breathing. [17] They provided in-person sessions, adjusting the music's volume and speed in accordance with the patient's breathing and pulse rate. [17] As a result, significant changes in breathing and heart rates occurred, and anxiety levels decreased. [17] Our results show the same thing. According to a recent study, there was a noticeable drop in anxiety, which allowed the patient on ventilator care to listen to music whenever they wanted. [18]

Stress is a common occurrence for patients in critical care units, particularly for those on mechanical ventilation. [18] The patient's general health and capacity to recover may be negatively impacted by anxiety. [18] Patients who are critically ill usually react well to music interventions, which are widely used stress-reduction techniques in all branches of medicine. It can reduce the stress response, cause a general relaxation response, and lessen anxiety during mechanical breathing without the need for medicine. [3] Thus, the results of this study suggest that the parameters associated with basal cardiovascular are significantly improved by music intervention. Thus, it also decreases serum cortisol and IL-1, thereby reducing anxiety in COVID-19 patients.

The study has limitations due to its methodological quality and smaller sample size. Thus, a larger sample size study needs to be performed in the future for in-depth knowledge. No standard tools exist to measure the impact of music interventions on patients' well-being and the interventions themselves. As our study is primarily comprised of males, we recommend a study that is exclusively performed on females.

Conclusions

The study reveals that music intervention in hospitalized COVID-19 patients significantly decreases their heart rate, systolic blood pressure, diastolic blood pressure, and serum cortisol, thus improving basal cardiovascular functions and stress levels overall. The study supports the integration of music intervention into clinical practice, despite challenges in working conditions and a lack of literature on its experiences with COVID patients. It demonstrates the feasibility of music intervention as a form of support in extreme situations when applied appropriately. The positive patient feedback and clinical impact suggest further investigation into its potential to promote comfort, relaxation, lower anxiety, affect physiological outcomes, and enhance psychosocial support.

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